

Mini Review

Nutritional properties and plausible benefits of Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) on bone metabolism and osteoimmunology: a mini-review

Abdelhafid Nani ^{1*} , Meriem Belarbi ², Naim Akhtar Khan ³ , Aziz Hichami ³ ¹ Laboratory of Saharan Natural Resources, African University Ahmed Draia, Adrar, Algeria² Laboratory of Natural Products, University of Abou-Bekr Belkaid, Tlemcen, Algeria³ U1231 INSERM/Université de Bourgogne-Franche Comté (UBFC)/Agro-Sup, Physiologie de la Nutrition & Toxicologie, France

Abstract

Bone is a hard connective tissue that undergoes a systematic renewal. This highly dynamic organ is made up of four different types of cells, however, bone formation is commonly attributed to osteoblasts and bone resorption to osteoclasts. Bone tissue formation occurs during embryonic development and in certain post-birth pathological conditions. The immune system could influence the functions of bone cells, and the crosstalk between hematopoietic, immune, and bone cells is known as osteoimmunology. Indeed, cytokines produced by immune cells, including TNF- α and IL-6, are critically implicated in bone pathogenesis. It is well established that diet plays an important role in bone health and function. Indeed, antioxidant nutraceuticals-rich diet, of which pearl millet is one, can be effective in treating osteoporosis. Pearl millet (PM) is an African native cereal that constitutes the staple food for African Sahel region inhabitants as well as for many peoples in rural regions in India. Pearl millet grains content in amino acids, minerals, and phytochemicals may contribute to promoting bone health and metabolism. Accordingly, in the current review, we discuss the putative effects of PM nutrients, with a focus on polyphenols, on bone metabolism and osteoimmunology. In the light of our previous studies and others from literature, we suggest that PM whole grains can be effective in the prevention and management of bone pathogenesis.

Keywords: PM whole grains, nutrients, polyphenols, osteoblasts, osteoclasts, osteoimmunology, TNF- α .

Received: August 11, 2020 / Accepted: December 08, 2020 / Published: December 27, 2020

1. Introduction

Made up of 206 bones, the skeletal system, or skeleton, of human body plays a key role in positioning and protecting the other organ systems, supporting the body, and storing minerals. Inside certain bones, hematopoiesis, which corresponds to the process by which blood cells are formed, occurs within the bone marrow¹. Bone tissue formation occurs during embryonic development and in certain post-birth pathological conditions, including fracture². Indeed, a complex process called bone remodeling by which four types of cells: osteoblasts, osteocytes, bone lining cells, and osteoclasts act together to heal the fracture³. A failure in bone remodeling can cause pathological destructive bone diseases such as osteoporosis that predominantly affects menopausal women⁴. Bone resorption (destruction) by osteoclasts is the first phase in the complex process of bone remodeling³. For some time, given that osteoclasts are derived from immune cells, the relationship between immune and skeletal systems has been clear. Therefore, the study of interactions between these systems is defined as osteoimmunology⁵. Cytokines including TNF- α and IL-6 play fundamental roles in osteoimmunology⁶. It is now well established that TNF- α and IL-6 constitute important modulators of immune-mediated bone diseases including postmenopausal osteoporosis⁷. The use of drugs for osteoporosis-related fracture has been criticized chiefly for its costs and side effects, whereas, nutritional-based strategies are highly

recommended⁸. Indeed, it is well established that antioxidant nutraceuticals-rich herbal medicines such as pearl millet can be effective in treating osteoporosis.

Pearl millet or *Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) is a minor cereal domesticated somewhere in West Africa for almost 4500 years ago, then it has spread to other continents over time⁹. Pearl millet is one of the four major types of millet family¹⁰. In addition to the valid '*Pennisetum glaucum*' taxonomic name, pearl millet is also called *Pennisetum americanum* or *Pennisetum typhoides*¹¹. It is called *Bajara* in India¹², *Bechna* in local south-west Algerian Arabic, or *Innelly* in *Zenatia*, a berber dialect. Moreover, pearl millet has many vernacular names in Sub-Saharan Africa¹³. Pearl millet grain is the staple food for African Sahel region inhabitants as well as for many peoples in rural regions in India. Previous studies have already demonstrated the antioxidant¹⁴, immunomodulatory¹⁵, and anti-cancer proprieties of pearl millet¹⁶. In the traditional medicine of the South of Algeria, mild millet is used alone or in combination with other medicinal plants to boost bone remodeling. Herein, in light of researches which have been undertaken on pearl millet nutritional composition and impact on metabolism, the current review aims to provide a body of evidence on the effectiveness of pearl millet grains for bone homeostasis.

2. Overview on bone metabolism and osteoimmunology

Osteogenesis is a process by which connective bone tissue is formed from bone marrow mesenchymal stem cell during both fetal and postnatal periods¹⁷, whereas, bone remodeling is a complex process involving bone resorption by osteoclasts and bone formation by osteoblasts¹. Bone remodeling occurs along the bone normal development and following certain traumas like fracture which is the most frequent traumatic large-organ injury¹⁸. This process occurs in three consecutive phases: osteoclastic resorption, reversal period, and osteoblastic formation¹⁹. The process of bone remodeling promotes the fracture healing through the coordination of several cell types chiefly osteoclasts, osteocytes, bone lining cells, and osteoblasts which are all assembled into a temporary anatomic structure called basic multicellular unit (BMU)²⁰. Furthermore, molecules including parathyroid hormone (PTH), bone morphogenetic proteins (BMP) which belong to the transforming growth factor beta (TGFbeta) superfamily, insulin-like growth factors (IGFs), osteoprotegerin (OPG), receptor activator of NF-kappa B ligand (RANKL), alkaline phosphatase, prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), Runx2, and cytokines are involved as well in bone remodeling resulting in restored bone integrity¹.

Recently, there has been an increasing interest in the immune regulation of bone metabolism. Thus, the study of interactions between skeletal and immune systems is defined as osteoimmunology in which osteoblasts play a pivotal role⁵. Indeed, osteoblasts can secrete several cytokines including macrophage chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), TGF- β , IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α in response to various stimuli^{1,6}. It is now well established that TNF- α and IL-6 constitute important modulators of immune-mediated bone diseases including postmenopausal osteoporosis⁷. TNF- α is produced mainly by monocytes, but can also be secreted by osteoblasts, T cells and other cell types²². Nanes *et al.*²³ have shown that higher concentrations of TNF- α stimulate osteoclastogenesis through receptor activator of nuclear factor κ B receptor (RANK)/RANKL pathway. In line with these findings, TNF- α suppressed osteoblast differentiation through NF- κ B and mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) pathways. In addition, TNF- α can stimulate NF- κ B signaling and inhibit Wnt signaling that is the main canonical pathway of osteoblastic differentiation²³. TNF- α also suppressed BMP-2-induced osteoblast differentiation and activated NF- κ B signaling²⁴. Moreover, TNF- α mitigated the expression of Runx2 transcription factor, a downstream effector of p38 MAPK, which is required for osteoblast differentiation²⁵. TNF- α induced the production of IL-6 pro-inflammatory cytokine and nitric oxide (NO), which modulates osteoclast recruitment and activity, in osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 cells²⁶. Indeed, TNF- α induced oxidative stress that stimulates osteoclastogenesis and enhances bone resorption²⁷. IL-6 is another cytokine that exhibits many roles in bone physiology²⁸. IL-6 has been reported to promote osteoclastogenesis through enhanced RANKL expression in response to sustained PTH elevation, vitamin D3, and ovariectomy³. Moreover, a combination of IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-

1 β treatment has been found to increase RANKL/OPG ratio in SCP-1 human osteoblastic cell line accompanied with significant increase in osteoclast resorption activity²⁹.

Although the above-mentioned cytokines have been established to modulate bone resorption, they may have a dual role in bone remodeling²². Indeed, they are also recognized to boost osteoblast differentiation and contribute to bone formation⁷.

Figure 1: Illustration of some TNF- α -mediated biological processes of bone. BMP-2: bone morphogenetic proteins, NF- κ B: nuclear factor κ B, MAPK: mitogen-activated protein kinases, OPG: osteoprotegerin, RANK: receptor activator of NF- κ B, RANKL: receptor activator of NF- κ B ligand, Runx2; Runt-related transcription factor 2, TNF- α : tumor necrosis factor-alpha, Wnt: Wingless type

3. Nutrient composition of pearl millet grains

PM is an important source of food security, nutrition and health in the arid and semi-arid tropics³⁰. Indeed, PM grains possess considerable amounts of proteins, fat, carbohydrates, minerals, vitamins, and phytochemicals^{15,31,32}.

3.1 Proteins

Protein content in PM grains ranges between 8.8 and 16.1 %^{31,32}. It has been established that cereal grains are notably deficient in lysine which is an essential amino acid that must be supplied from an exogenous diet³³. Yet, PM contains a balanced amino acid profile with considerable amounts of lysine that can reach 2.9 g/ 100 g proteins³⁴. Moreover, arginine that can be interconverted to proline and ultimately incorporated into collagen is estimated at 4.23 g/ 100 g proteins in PM grains³¹. Interestingly, digestibility of these essential amino acids has been found higher in pearl millet than in corn³⁵. Civitelli *et al.*³⁶ argue for an adequate lysine intake for the management of fractures and osteoporosis due to its stimulating effects on intestinal calcium absorption and renal conversion. In the same vein, Fini *et al.*³⁷ emphasize the importance of lysine and arginine for bone remodeling, in part, through improving type I collagen synthesis by osteoblasts in both normal and osteopenic bone.

3.2 Lipids

PM grains contain the highest level of lipids as compared to wheat, barley, rye, and sorghum³². Our earlier findings showed that lipids represent 4.5 % in PM grains, and more than 72% of the fatty acids are unsaturated¹⁵. Among essential fatty acids, α -linolenic acid occupied only 3.2 % of total fatty acids in PM grains, however, this amount is the highest when compared to maize and rice³⁸. Recently, it has been shown that α -linolenic acid-rich flaxseed oil improve HFD-induced bone loss, most likely by promoting osteogenesis³⁹. On the other hand, T cells activation, which may delay fracture healing, is abolished by PM lipids treatment¹⁵.

3.3 Starch and dietary fibers

Starch is one of the major nutrients in cereals, and it constitutes the main source of energy in plant foods³². PM starch content is comparable to that of sorghum which has starch content of about 67.5%. However, it is relatively higher than that of barley and rye (53.6% and 58.0%, respectively)³². The portion of starch that resists digestion as it passes through the gastrointestinal tract is known as resistant starch⁴⁰. There is an increasing interest in resistant starch for both its potential health benefits and functional properties⁴¹. A recent study has shown that resistant starch attenuates bone loss in ovariectomized mice in part by regulating bone-marrow inflammation⁴². Interestingly, resistant starch proportion can reach 6.14 % in heat-moisture treated-PM starch⁴³. Resistant starch is commonly grouped with dietary fibers on the basis of their indigestibility⁴⁴. Thereby, PM whole grains showed a reasonable level of dietary fiber estimated to be 14.95 %³².

3.4 Minerals

Minerals are minor constituents in cereal grains, however, they are as important as other nutrients⁴⁵. The mineral content of PM whole grains ranges between 1.82 and 2.1 %^{32,46}. The overall mineral content in PM grains is high when compared to commonly consumed cereals as reported by Nambiar *et al.*¹². Indeed, PM whole grains contained phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and potassium (K) with an amount of 2879, 508.6, 1488, and 2798 mg/kg, respectively³². Moreover, PM grains contains trace minerals such as zinc and iron with a concentration of 65.9 and 199.8 mg/kg, respectively³², however, processing such as decortication influences the overall mineral content in PM⁴⁷. Minerals contribute in the transformation of type I collagen produced from osteoblasts to mineralized extracellular matrix in bone tissue⁴⁸. The impact of dietary intake of calcium, magnesium, phosphorus, and potassium on bone development had been extensively discussed⁴⁹. Hence, it is obvious that a rational intake of foods that are rich in minerals such as calcium and phosphorus is positively associated with bone formation and density⁵⁰. In addition to its role as cofactor of a large number of enzymes, zinc may exert protective properties against bone loss by suppressing osteoclastogenesis⁵¹.

3.5 Vitamins

Nambiar *et al.* reported that PM whole grains are important sources of certain vitamins, mainly some of the B-complex vitamins¹². Indeed, levels of thiamine (B1), riboflavin (B2), Niacin (B3), and folic acid (B9) are approximately 0.33, 0.25, 2.3, and 0.046 mg/100 g, respectively. Thus, vitamin A and vitamin C occupies a proportion of 0.13 and 0.73 mg/100 g, respectively in PM whole grains^{12,31}. The so-called B-vitamins and vitamin C are water-soluble, and their function as coenzyme is the most salient characteristic of this class of vitamins. Whereas vitamin C is well known for its antioxidant proprieties, the fat-soluble vitamin A, also known as provitamin A and preformed vitamin A, exerts much of its effects both on rhodopsin conformational change following light-induced bleaching and at the gene level⁵².

3.6 Phytochemicals

Phytochemicals or plant secondary metabolites are plant-derived chemicals or compounds. Hence, bioactive phytochemicals that protect or promote health are known as nutraceuticals which occur at the intersection of food and pharmaceutical industries⁵³. The well-documented phytochemicals are mainly phenolics (or polyphenols), alkaloids, and terpenes⁵⁴. Cereals contain significant amounts of phytochemicals⁴⁵ among which phenolics are the most studied in PM grains^{15,16,32,55–58}. Previous researches have shown that total phenolic content in PM whole grains ranges from 1660 to 2580 μg gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g DM^{15,59}. Furthermore, flavonoids are estimated to be 2350 μg catechin equivalents (CE)/g DM⁵⁹. Our previous research has demonstrated that hydroxycinnamic acids are the most abundant phenolic compound in PM whole grains¹⁵. There is an increasing body of evidence that polyphenols, including hydroxycinnamic acids, are effective in improving bone health through promoting bone remodeling and mitigating the damaging effects of oxidative stress that takes part in bone-resorptive processes⁶⁰. In addition, PM polyphenols modulated MAPK pathways both in osteoblasts and T cells^{15,16}.

4. Pearl millet grains phenolics benefits on bone health and functions

Recently, a big interest has been given to traditional diet which has an impact on the prevention and management of a number of pathologies including rheumatic diseases^{61,62}. As far as bone tissue is concerned, epigenetic alterations have been established as key factors of osteogenesis, homeostasis, and diseases of pathologic bone remodeling^{63,64}. Indeed, there is a common agreement that nutrients can regulate gene expression in many biological processes^{61,64}. Among nutrients, dietary polyphenols have been reported to have a positive impact both on bone health and function⁶⁰. Several polyphenol-rich foods including olive, extra virgin olive oil, green tea, plum, and blueberry, have been shown to exert an osteoprotective activity under normal and inflammatory conditions^{62,65–68}. There are many PM-based traditional diets in different regions in Africa and Asia^{47,57,69,70}. According to our previous studies, PM grains are rich in

polyphenols that exert immunomodulatory and anti-cancer, against osteosarcoma, activities^{15,16}. To the best of our knowledge, no single study discussed the potential effects of PM grains on bone yet.

Beside the afore-mentioned benefits of PM nutrients on bone remodeling, in this section we emphasize the plausible benefits of PM phenolic compounds on bone remodeling and osteoimmunology. Some studies have already demonstrated the effects of ferulic acid, a major phenolic compound in PM grains, on gene expression of the principal proteins that play a pivotal role in bone remodeling and osteoimmunology chiefly RANKL and NF- κ B⁷¹. Ferulic acid promoted osteogenesis of human bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (MSC) by up-regulating β -catenin, which constitutes the major player of Wnt signalling, expression and activity⁷². Ferulic acid treatment also increased the expression of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), Runx2, and Ostrix (Osx) osteoblast markers in MSC⁷². Another research has revealed that ferulic acid can protect against osteoporosis in glucocorticoid-treated neonatal rats in part through inhibition of NF- κ B signaling⁷³. On the other hand, ferulic acid suppressed osteoclast differentiation in RAW 264.7 monocyte/macrophage cells via the inhibition of RANKL dependent NF- κ B signaling pathway⁷¹. The same authors showed that ferulic acid mitigates the gene expression of TRAP, MMP-9 and Cathepsin K which all mediate bone resorption activity of mature osteoclasts⁷¹.

Figure 2: Putative effects of PM phenolics on bone metabolism. ALP: alkaline phosphatase, COX-2: cyclooxygenase-2, IGF-1: insulin-like growth factor-1, IL-1 β : interleukin-1 β , IL-6: interleukin-6, iNOS: inducible nitric oxide synthase, OPG: osteoprotegerin, Osx: Ostrix, NF- κ B: nuclear factor κ B, RANKL: receptor activator of NF- κ B ligand, Runx2: Runt-related transcription factor 2, TNF- α : tumor necrosis factor-alpha, Wnt: Wingless type

p-coumaric acid, the most abundant phenolic compound in PM grains¹⁵, stimulates longitudinal growth of the long bone through increasing the expression of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) in adolescent male rats⁷⁴. Neog and Rasool⁷⁵ demonstrated that p-coumaric inhibits osteoclastogenesis and bone resorption by enhancing OPG/RANKL ratio and down-regulating iNOS and TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β , and COX-2 inflammatory mediators in the rheumatoid arthritis animal model. Hence, inhibiting TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β cytokines expression by the suppression of NF- κ B

signaling may improve bone loss and other complications⁷⁶. Interestingly, the inhibition effects of bone resorption by green tea polyphenols was associated with reduced splenic TNF- α and COX-2 expression in a chronic inflammation-induced bone loss model⁶⁶. Green tea polyphenols also alleviated ROS-induced oxidative stress in cultured rat clavalial osteoblast⁷⁷. Dried plum polyphenols restored TNF- α -dependent decrease of Runx2, Osterix and IGF-I levels in osteoblast⁷⁸. Overall, PM phenolics may promote osteogenesis and mitigate osteoclastogenesis in part through modulating oxidative stress, Wnt and NF- κ B signaling pathways.

5. Conclusion

Polyphenols of PM grains may contribute to the prevention, management and treatment of some bone pathogenesis by their positive impact on osteoimmunology revealed by their immunomodulatory effects. However, the synergetic effect between whole-grain PM nutrients is possibly more powerful than that of individual components. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies should be conducted to check the impact of PM nutrients on bone biology in normal and pathological conditions.

Limitations: the putative effects of the pearl millet grains on bone homeostasis were based on those exerted by some pearl millet nutrients and phytochemicals. Yet, the detailed mechanisms ought to be checked experimentally.

Authors' contribution: A.N. and M.B. conceived the study. A.N performed the literature search and prepared the manuscript. N.A.K and A.H designed the study. A.H edited and reviewed the manuscript. All authors approved the final version before submission, have read and agreed to be published version of the manuscript.

Funding: Not applicable

Conflicts of Interest: the authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- Lorenzo J, Horowitz M, Choi Y, Takayanagi H, Schett G. Osteoimmunology: Interactions of the Immune and Skeletal Systems. Academic Press, 2nd Edition: 2015: pp 376. ISBN-13: 978-0128005712
- Katagiri T, Tsukamoto S, Osawa K, Kokabu S. Ligand-Receptor Interactions and Their Implications in Delivering Certain Signaling for Bone Regeneration. In: A Tissue Regeneration Approach to Bone and Cartilage Repair. Springer; 2015:1-15.
- Bellido, T., Plotkin, L. I., & Bruzzaniti, A. (2019). Bone Cells. *Basic and Applied Bone Biology*, 37-55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-813259-3.00003-8>
- Sinaki M, Pfeifer M. Non-Pharmacological Management of Osteoporosis: Exercise, Nutrition, Fall and Fracture Prevention. Springer: 2017: pp 262. ISBN-13 : 978-3319852973
- Charles, J. F., Nakamura, M. C., & Humphrey, M. B. (2019). Bone and the Immune System (Osteoimmunology). *Basic and Applied Bone Biology*, 333-347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-813259-3.00017-8>
- Lian, J. B., Gravallese, E. M., & Stein, G. S. (2011). Osteoblasts and their Signaling Pathways. *Osteoimmunology*, 101-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-375670-1.10005-6>

7. Wang, T., & He, C. (2020). TNF- α and IL-6: The Link between Immune and Bone System. *Current drug targets*, 21(3), 213–227. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389450120666190821161259>
8. Kelly L, Kelly HB. The Healthy Bones Nutrition Plan and Cookbook: How to Prepare and Combine Whole Foods to Prevent and Treat Osteoporosis Naturally. Chelsea Green Publishing: 2016: pp 304. ISBN-13 : 978-1603586245
9. Winchell, F., Brass, M., Manzo, A., Beldados, A., Perna, V., Murphy, C., Stevens, C., & Fuller, D. Q. (2018). On the Origins and Dissemination of Domesticated Sorghum and Pearl Millet across Africa and into India: a View from the Butana Group of the Far Eastern Sahel. *African Archaeological Review*, 35(4), 483-505. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10437-018-9314-2>
10. Amadou, I., Gounga, M., & Le, G.-W. (2013, May 1). Millets: Nutritional composition, some health benefits and processing - A review. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 25(7), 501-508. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.9755/ejfa.v25i7.12045>
11. Longtau, SR. (2008). Linguistics and archaeology: historical inferences from cognates for bulrush millet in Plateau and a review of research methodology. *Festschrift in honour of Prof Conrad Brann*. Published online :233-255.
12. Nambiar, V.S., Dhaduk, J.J., Sareen, S., Shahu, T., & Desai, R. (2011). Potential Functional Implications of Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) in Health and Disease. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 1(10), 62-67. https://www.japsonline.com/admin/php/uploads/299_pdf.pdf
13. Blench, R. (2012). Finger millet: the contribution of vernacular names towards its prehistory. *Archaeological and Anthropological Sciences*, 8(1), 79-88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-012-0103-6>
14. Salar, R. K., Purewal, S. S., & Sandhu, K. S. (2017). Fermented pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) with in vitro DNA damage protection activity, bioactive compounds and antioxidant potential. *Food Research International*, 100, 204-210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.08.045>
15. Nani, A., Belarbi, M., Ksouri-Megdiche, W., Abdoul-Azize, S., Benammar, C., Ghiringhelli, F., Hichami, A., & Khan, N. A. (2015). Effects of polyphenols and lipids from *Pennisetum glaucum* grains on T-cell activation: modulation of Ca(2+) and ERK1/ERK2 signaling. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 15, 426. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-015-0946-3>
16. Nani, A., Belarbi, M., Murtaza, B., Benammar, C., Merghoub, T., Rialland, M., Akhtar Khan, N., & Hichami, A. (2019). Polyphenols from *Pennisetum glaucum* grains induce MAP kinase phosphorylation and cell cycle arrest in human osteosarcoma cells. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 54, 422-432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2019.01.042>
17. Jo, C. H., Yoon, P. W., Kim, H., Kang, K. S., & Yoon, K. S. (2013). Comparative evaluation of in vivo osteogenic differentiation of fetal and adult mesenchymal stem cell in rat critical-sized femoral defect model. *Cell and Tissue Research*, 353(1), 41-52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00441-013-1619-5>
18. Cladis, D. P., Li, S., Reddivari, L., Cox, A., Ferruzzi, M. G., & Weaver, C. M. (2020). A 90 day oral toxicity study of blueberry polyphenols in ovariectomized sprague-dawley rats. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 139, 111254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fct.2020.111254>
19. Hadjidakis, D. J., & Androulakis, I. I. (2006). Bone remodeling. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1092, 385–396. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1365.035>
20. Jilka, R. L. (2003). Biology of the basic multicellular unit and the pathophysiology of osteoporosis. *Medical and Pediatric Oncology*, 41(3), 182-185. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpo.10334>
21. DiMeglio, L. A., & Imel, E. A. (2019). Calcium and Phosphate. *Basic and Applied Bone Biology*, 257-282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-813259-3.00013-0>
22. Nanes, M. S. (2016). Osteoimmunology and the Osteoblast. *Osteoimmunology*, 71-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-800571-2.00005-0>
23. Osta, B., Benedetti, G., & Miossec, P. (2014). Classical and Paradoxical Effects of TNF- α on Bone Homeostasis. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 5, 48. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2014.00048>
24. B Bai, F., Chen, X., Yang, H., & Xu, H. G. (2018). Acetyl-11-Keto- β -Boswellic Acid Promotes Osteoblast Differentiation by Inhibiting Tumor Necrosis Factor- α and Nuclear Factor- κ B Activity. *The Journal of Craniofacial Surgery*, 29(7), 1996–2002. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SCS.00000000000004691>
25. Yu, L., Xu, Y., Qu, H., Yu, Y., Li, W., Zhao, Y., & Qiu, G. (2018). Decrease of MiR-31 induced by TNF- α inhibitor activates SATB2/RUNX2 pathway and promotes osteogenic differentiation in ethanol-induced osteonecrosis. *Journal of Cellular Physiology*, 234(4), 4314-4326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcp.27210>
26. Choi E. M. (2007). Apigenin increases osteoblastic differentiation and inhibits tumor necrosis factor-alpha-induced production of interleukin-6 and nitric oxide in osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 cells. *Die Pharmazie*, 62(3), 216–220.
27. Almeida, M., Han, L., Ambrogini, E., Weinstein, R. S., & Manolagas, S. C. (2011). Glucocorticoids and tumor necrosis factor α increase oxidative stress and suppress Wnt protein signaling in osteoblasts. *The Journal of biological chemistry*, 286(52), 44326–44335. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M111.283481>
28. Sims, N. A., & Martin, T. J. (2020). The osteoblast lineage. *Principles of Bone Biology*, 89-110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-814841-9.00004-x>
29. Blaschke, M., Koepp, R., Cortis, J., Komrakova, M., Schieker, M., Hempel, U., & Siggelkow, H. (2018). IL-6, IL-1 β , and TNF- α only in combination influence the osteoporotic phenotype in Crohn's patients via bone formation and bone resorption. *Advances in clinical and experimental medicine : official organ Wroclaw Medical University*, 27(1), 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.17219/acem/67561>
30. Jukanti, A. K., Gowda, C. L. L., Rai, K. N., Manga, V. K., & Bhatt, R. K. (2016). Crops that feed the world 11. Pearl Millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.) : an important source of food security, nutrition and health in the arid and semi-arid tropics. *Food Security*, 8(2), 307-329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-016-0557-y>
31. Malleshi, N.G., Klopfenstein, C.F. (1998). Nutrient composition, amino acid and vitamin contents of malted sorghum, pearl millet, finger millet and their rootlets. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition*, 49(6), 415-422. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09637489809086420>

32. Ragae, S., Abdelaal, E., & Noaman, M. (2006). Antioxidant activity and nutrient composition of selected cereals for food use. *Food Chemistry*, 98(1), 32-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2005.04.039>
33. Shewry, P. R. (2007). Improving the protein content and composition of cereal grain. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 46(3), 239-250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2007.06.006>
34. Serna-Saldivar, S.O., Clegg, C., Rooney, L.W. (1994). Effects of parboiling and decortication on the nutritional value of sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.). *J Cereal Sci*, 19(1), 83-89.
35. Adeola, O., & Orban, J. I. (1995). Chemical composition and nutrient digestibility of pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) fed to growing pigs. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 22(2), 177-184. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0733-5210\(95\)90048-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0733-5210(95)90048-9)
36. Civitelli, R., Villareal, D. T., Agnusdei, D., Nardi, P., Avioli, L. V., & Gennari, C. (1992). Dietary L-lysine and calcium metabolism in humans. *Nutrition (Burbank, Los Angeles County, Calif.)*, 8(6), 400-405.
37. Fini, M., Torricelli, P., Giavaresi, G., Carpi, A., Nicolini, A., & Giardino, R. (2001). Effect of L-lysine and L-arginine on primary osteoblast cultures from normal and osteopenic rats. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie*, 55(4), 213-220. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0753-3322\(01\)00054-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0753-3322(01)00054-3)
38. Adeyeye, A., & Ajewole, K. (1992). Chemical composition and fatty acid profiles of cereals in Nigeria. *Food Chemistry*, 44(1), 41-44. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146\(92\)90255-z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146(92)90255-z)
39. Chen, F., Wang, Y., Wang, H., Dong, Z., Wang, Y., Zhang, M., Li, J., Shao, S., Yu, C., Huan, Z., & Xu, J. (2019). Flaxseed oil ameliorated high-fat-diet-induced bone loss in rats by promoting osteoblastic function in rat primary osteoblasts. *Nutrition & Metabolism*, 16(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12986-019-0393-0>
40. Nugent, A. P. (2005). Health properties of resistant starch. *Nutrition Bulletin*, 30(1), 27-54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-3010.2005.00481.x>
41. Fuentes-Zaragoza, E., Riquelme-Navarrete, M. J., Sánchez-Zapata, E., & Pérez-Álvarez, J. A. (2010). Resistant starch as functional ingredient : A review. *Food Research International*, 43(4), 931-942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2010.02.004>
42. Tousen, Y., Matsumoto, Y., Nagahata, Y., Kobayashi, I., Inoue, M., & Ishimi, Y. (2019). Resistant Starch Attenuates Bone Loss in Ovariectomised Mice by Regulating the Intestinal Microbiota and Bone-Marrow Inflammation. *Nutrients*, 11(2), 297. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11020297>
43. Sharma, M., Yadav, D. N., Singh, A. K., & Tomar, S. K. (2015). Effect of Heat-Moisture Treatment on Resistant Starch Content as well as Heat and Shear Stability of Pearl Millet Starch. *Agricultural Research*, 411-419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40003-015-0177-3>
44. Shi Y-C, Maningat CC. Resistant Starch: Sources, Applications and Health Benefits. John Wiley & Sons: 2013: pp 3012. ISBN: 978-1-118-52875-4.
45. Arendt EK, Zannini E. *Cereal Grains for the Food and Beverage Industries*. Elsevier; Published online 2013. ISBN: 9780857094131. pp512
46. Adebisi, J. A., Obadina, A. O., Adebo, O. A., & Kayitesi, E. (2017). Comparison of nutritional quality and sensory acceptability of biscuits obtained from native, fermented, and malted pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) flour. *Food chemistry*, 232, 210-217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.04.020>
47. Lestienne, I., Buisson, M., Lullien-Pellerin, V., Picq, C., & Trèche, S. (2007). Losses of nutrients and anti-nutritional factors during abrasive decortication of two pearl millet cultivars (*Pennisetum glaucum*). *Food Chemistry*, 100(4), 1316-1323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2005.11.027>
48. Bradley EW, Westendorf JJ, Van Wijnen AJ, Dudakovic A. Osteoblasts: function, development, and regulation. *Prim Metab Bone Dis Disord Miner Metab* John Wiley Sons, Inc Hoboken, NJ, USA. Published online 2018:31-37. ISBN: 9781119266563.
49. Winzenberg T, Jones G. Calcium, Vitamin D, and Other Nutrients During Growth. *Prim Metab Bone Dis Disord Miner Metab*. Published online 2018:135.
50. Cuadrado-Soto, E., López-Sobaler, A. M., Jiménez-Ortega, A. I., Aparicio, A., Bermejo, L. M., Hernández-Ruiz, Á., Lara Villoslada, F., Leis, R., Martínez de Victoria, E., Moreno, J. M., Ruiz-López, M. D., Soto-Méndez, M. J., Valero, T., Varela-Moreiras, G., Gil, Á., & Ortega, R. M. (2020). Usual Dietary Intake, Nutritional Adequacy and Food Sources of Calcium, Phosphorus, Magnesium and Vitamin D of Spanish Children Aged One to <10 Years. Findings from the EsNuPI Study. *Nutrients*, 12(6), 1787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12061787>
51. Amin, N., Clark, C., Taghizadeh, M., & Djafarnejad, S. (2020). Zinc supplements and bone health: The role of the RANKL-RANK axis as a therapeutic target. *Journal of trace elements in medicine and biology : organ of the Society for Minerals and Trace Elements (GMS)*, 57, 126417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2019.126417>
52. Gerald F. Combs, Jr. & James P. McClung The vitamins fundamental aspects in nutrition and Health. Published online 2019. ISBN: 978-0-12-802965-7. pp628.
53. Prakash D, Sharma G. *Phytochemicals of Nutraceutical Importance*. CABI; 2014.
54. Ramawat KG, Mérillon J-M. *Natural Products: Phytochemistry, Botany and Metabolism of Alkaloids, Phenolics and Terpenes*. Springer; 2013.
55. Nambiar, V. S., Sareen, N., Daniel, M., & Gallego, E. B. (2012). Flavonoids and phenolic acids from pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) based foods and their functional implications. *Functional Foods in Health and Disease*, 2(7), 251. <https://doi.org/10.31989/ffhd.v2i7.85>
56. S Shahidi, F., & Chandrasekara, A. (2013). Millet grain phenolics and their role in disease risk reduction and health promotion: A review. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 5(2), 570-581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2013.02.004>
57. Tako, E., Reed, S. M., Budiman, J., Hart, J. J., & Glahn, R. P. (2015). Higher iron pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.) provides more absorbable iron that is limited by increased polyphenolic content. *Nutrition Journal*, 14(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2891-14-11>
58. Hassan, Z. M., Sebola, N. A., & Mabelebele, M. (2020). Evaluating the physical and chemical contents of millets obtained from South Africa and Zimbabwe. *CyTA - Journal of Food*, 18(1), 662-669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19476337.2020.1818831>

59. Hithamani, G., & Srinivasan, K. (2014). Effect of domestic processing on the polyphenol content and bioaccessibility in finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*) and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*). *Food Chemistry*, 164, 55-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.04.107>
60. R Rao, L. G., Kang, N., & Rao, A. V. (2012). Polyphenol Antioxidants and Bone Health: A Review. *Phytochemicals - A Global Perspective of Their Role in Nutrition and Health*, 467-486. <https://doi.org/10.5772/39287>
61. Shanahan C. Deep Nutrition: Why Your Genes Need Traditional Food. Flatiron Books: 2017: pp 512.
62. Cardoso, C., Santos, A., Rosa, L., Mendonça, C. R., Vitorino, P., Peixoto, M., & Silveira, É. A. (2020). Effect of Extra Virgin Olive Oil and Traditional Brazilian Diet on the Bone Health Parameters of Severely Obese Adults: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nutrients*, 12(2), 403. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12020403>
63. Raut, N., Wicks, S. M., Lawal, T. O., & Mahady, G. B. (2019). Epigenetic regulation of bone remodeling by natural compounds. *Pharmacological Research*, 147, 104350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2019.104350>
64. Pérez-Castrillón, J. L., & Riancho del Moral, J. A. (2020). Nutrients and Gene Expression Affecting Bone Metabolism. *Principles of Nutrigenetics and Nutrigenomics*, 489-495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-804572-5.00064-1>
65. Puel, C., Mathey, J., Agalias, A., Kati-coulibaly, S., Mardon, J., Obled, C., Davicco, M.-J., Lebecque, P., Horcajada, M.-N., Skaltsounis, A. L., & Coxam, V. (2006). Dose-response study of effect of oleuropein, an olive oil polyphenol, in an ovariectomy/inflammation experimental model of bone loss in the rat. *Clinical Nutrition*, 25(5), 859-868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2006.03.009>
66. Shen, C.-L., Yeh, J. K., Cao, J. J., Tatum, O. L., Dagda, R. Y., & Wang, J.-S. (2010). Green tea polyphenols mitigate bone loss of female rats in a chronic inflammation-induced bone loss model. *The Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry*, 21(10), 968-974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnutbio.2009.08.002>
67. Hagiwara, K., Goto, T., Araki, M., Miyazaki, H., & Hagiwara, H. (2011). Olive polyphenol hydroxytyrosol prevents bone loss. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 662(1-3), 78-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2011.04.023>
68. Graef, J. L., Ouyang, P., Wang, Y., Rendina-Ruedy, E., Lerner, M. R., Marlow, D., Lucas, E. A., & Smith, B. J. (2018). Dried plum polyphenolic extract combined with vitamin K and potassium restores trabecular and cortical bone in osteopenic model of postmenopausal bone loss. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 42, 262-270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jff.2017.12.057>
69. Huey, S. L., Venkatramanan, S., Udipi, S. A., Finkelstein, J. L., Ghugre, P., Haas, J. D., Thakker, V., Thorat, A., Salvi, A., Kurpad, A. V., & Mehta, S. (2017). Acceptability of Iron- and Zinc-Biofortified Pearl Millet (Dhanashakti)-Based [corrected] Complementary Foods among Children in an Urban Slum of Mumbai, India. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 4, 39. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2017.00039>
70. Alyami, J., Whitehouse, E., Yakubov, G. E., Pritchard, S. E., Hoad, C.L., Blackshaw, E., Heissam, K., Cordon, S. M., Bligh, H., Spiller, R.C., Macdonald, I.A., Aithal, G.P., Gowland, P. A., Taylor, M.A., & Marciani, L. (2019). Glycaemic, gastrointestinal, hormonal and appetitive responses to pearl millet or oats porridge breakfasts: a randomised, crossover trial in healthy humans. *The British journal of nutrition*, 122(10), 1142-1154. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S000711451900188>
71. Doss, H. M., Samarpita, S., Ganesan, R., & Rasool, M. (2018). Ferulic acid, a dietary polyphenol suppresses osteoclast differentiation and bone erosion via the inhibition of RANKL dependent NF- κ B signalling pathway. *Life sciences*, 207, 284-295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2018.06.013>
72. Du, K., Li, Z., Fang, X., Cao, T., & Xu, Y. (2017). Ferulic acid promotes osteogenesis of bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells by inhibiting microRNA-340 to induce β -catenin expression through hypoxia. *European journal of cell biology*, 96(6), 496-503. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejcb.2017.07.002>
73. Hou, T., Zhang, L., & Yang, X. (2019). Ferulic acid, a natural polyphenol, protects against osteoporosis by activating SIRT1 and NF- κ B in neonatal rats with glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie*, 120, 109205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2019.109205>
74. Lee, J. H., Chung, Y. H., Kim, H. H., Bang, J. S., Jung, T. W., Park, T., Park, J., Kim, U., Lee, S. H., & Jeong, J. H. (2018). p-Coumaric acid stimulates longitudinal bone growth through increasing the serum production and expression levels of insulin-like growth factor 1 in rats. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications*, 505(4), 1103-1106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2018.10.046>
75. Neog, M. K., & Rasool, M. (2018). Targeted delivery of p-coumaric acid encapsulated mannosylated liposomes to the synovial macrophages inhibits osteoclast formation and bone resorption in the rheumatoid arthritis animal model. *European journal of pharmaceuticals and biopharmaceutics : official journal of Arbeitsgemeinschaft fur Pharmazeutische Verfahrenstechnik e.V*, 133, 162-175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpb.2018.10.010>
76. Abu-Amer, Y., Darweh, I., & Otero, J. (2008). Role of the NF-kappaB axis in immune modulation of osteoclasts and bone loss. *Autoimmunity*, 41(3), 204-211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08916930701694543>
77. Park, Y. H., Han, D.-W., Suh, H., Ryu, G. H., Hyon, S.-H., Cho, B. K., & Park, J.-C. (2003). Protective effects of green tea polyphenol against reactive oxygen species-induced oxidative stress in cultured rat calvarial osteoblast. *Cell Biology and Toxicology*, 19(5), 325-337. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:cbto.000004986.51081.c5>
78. Bu, S. Y., Hunt, T. S., & Smith, B. J. (2009). Dried plum polyphenols attenuate the detrimental effects of TNF-alpha on osteoblast function coincident with up-regulation of Runx2, Osterix and IGF-I. *The Journal of nutritional biochemistry*, 20(1), 35-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnutbio.2007.11.012>

Cite this article as: Nani, A., Belarbi, M., Khan N.A., & Hichami A. (2020). Nutritional properties and plausible benefits of Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) on bone metabolism and osteoimmunology : a mini-review. *The North. African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research*, 04(09): 325-331. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396331>